

Employee Well-being: A Narrative Review

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 17, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 21, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Eudaimonic Well-Being, Employees' Performance, Organization</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5796535</p>	<p><i>This study examined eudaimonic well-being, the factors that affect it, and the relationship between eudaimonic well-being and job performance. In today's highly competitive environment, organizations have difficulty in maintaining the well-being and high work performance of their workers. Eudaimonic well-being (EWB) is a factor of usefulness that reflects the preferences of individuals for having a sense of meaning and purpose in their lives. This narrative review is based on 10 articles about eudaimonic well-being. The findings indicate that eudaimonic well-being is critical to the long-term viability of organizations and the individuals within them. An individual's level of eudaimonic well-being is closely linked to the type of job. The presence of eudaimonic well-being encourages individuals in the organization to be "purposeful" and productive, which consequently benefits the organization. A positive relationship between leadership and employees is significant for the employees' eudaimonic well-being. Further, it was suggested that organizations may increase their employees' performance through positive methods that emphasize characteristics which promote employees' eudaimonic well-being.</i></p>

Introduction

In today's highly competitive environment, organizations have difficulty in maintaining the well-being and high work performance of their employees. There are several approaches to improve work performance; however, those that include meaningfulness may be the most effective (Cartwright & Holmes, 2006). One of the primary goals of the organizational health framework is to promote well-being and work performance (Cotton, & Hart, 2003; Salas-Vallina, Alegre, & Lopez-Cabrales, 2021). Various studies have demonstrated that workplace well-being may have a significant impact on both individuals and businesses. In the workplace, the well-being of employees has been linked to productivity (Zelenski, Murphy, & Jenkins, 2008) and commitment to the organization (Fisher, 2010). Furthermore, (Mehta, 2021) (Faragher, Cass, & Cooper, 2013; Mehta, 2021), and discharges over their personal affairs in terms of satisfaction and overall quality of life (Bowling, Eschleman, & Wang, 2010), as well as satisfaction with individual life domains like family (Kinnunen et al., 2006).

'Eudaimonia' is an ancient Greek term that roughly translates as "happiness," but has also been defined as 'flourishing' (Huppert, & So, 2013), 'positive functioning' (Ryff, 1989), or 'worthwhileness' (Dolan, Layard, & Metcalfe, 2011). Based on the teachings of Socrates and Plato, Aristotle believed that the greatest good was eudaimonia or happiness comprised of virtue and pleasure. Eudaimonia was the ultimate level of personal character development; it was a great life. Subsequently, psychologists have revised the formula of Aristotle for happiness in terms of psycho-social meaning and pleasure, which is recognized as eudaimonic well-being (EWB) (Ryan, & Deci, 2001).

Eudaimonic well-being is described as the procedure of fulfilling one's maximum capabilities and being fully functional in the face of life's duties and obstacles. This complete functioning comprises cognitive components like behaving following firmly held norms and having a sense of meaning and purpose in life, as well as behavioral components like pursuing personal improvement and developing meaningful relationships (Ryan, & Deci, 2008). In studies utilizing multidimensional, eudaimonic conceptions of well-being, we find evidence for a link between contextual performance (Demerouti, Bakker, & Gevers, 2015), work performance (Zheng et al., 2015; Inceoglu et al., 2018), and task-oriented individual initiative (Hahn et al., 2012).

The eudaimonic method of becoming the best representation of oneself implies the purposeful use and development of one's strengths (Linley, 2013). As a result, through the completion of critical activities and services, the EWB might similarly demand active participation in organizational performance. The eudaimonic viewpoint, often known as psychological well-being, is concerned with optimal functioning and human progress (Sonnentag, 2015). This viewpoint is based on the idea that pleasure and happiness are not the only aspects of well-being. It happens when an individual's actions and cognitive abilities are genuine and in line with their strongly held values or beliefs (der Kinderen, & Khapova, 2020).

Good life and eudaimonic well-being are often synonymous, and sometimes they are not, but in either case, the two have a strong relationship: both are comprised of meaning and pleasure. The fulfillment of the

individual aims of employment is eudaimonic well-being. The six elements of eudaimonic well-being are development and growth, financial sustainability and flourishing, influence on the family as self-defined, impact on life construction, role in society, and self-expression. Ryff (1989) developed the multidimensional construct of psychological well-being from a eudaimonic viewpoint. The eudaimonic indicator ‘meaning’ shows job relevance and importance (Steger & Dik, 2010), and has been demonstrated to be a source for coping with work-related pressures (Clausen & Borg, 2011). Steptoe et al. (2007) discovered that eudaimonic well-being is closely related to adequate sleep and may mitigate the influence of psychosocial risk factors.

Benjamin et al. (2014) indicated that, out of over 100 distinct measures of subjective well-being, components of well-being related to eudaimonia were among the most desired. Being a decent, moral person and living according to personal principles ranked fourth, having a significant and valuable existence ranked tenth, and feeling that the things one accomplishes in one’s life are worthwhile placed twentieth. Adler et al. (2017) perform a similar revealed preference study and discover that most individuals tend to high subjective well-being over other “goods” like wealth and physical well-being, though they find a larger relative priority for subjective well-being over eudaimonic well-being. Similarly, Dolan, Kudrna, and Stone (2017) use the ATUS to demonstrate that life assessments (which can be seen as a substitute for subjective opinion) are more strongly connected with feelings of good and negative affect than with perceptions of meaningfulness. The data is thus mixed in the sense that eudaimonic well-being appears to be significant for utility, but to a lower extent than more hedonic or emotional components of well-being.

According to standard labor market theory, people are driven to work to earn an income, which in turn funds consumption, thus producing utility. Other features of a job, like working conditions or opportunities for advancement, may also contribute to its usefulness more explicitly. These incentives are extrinsic in the sense that they are acquired from personal rewards for labor rather than from the activity itself. For people who are driven by extrinsic incentives, work is a means to a goal rather than an end in itself. In conventional labor market models, this is the default assumption. According to self-determination theory (Ryan & Deci, 2000), situations that promote an individual’s feelings of independence, expertise, and belongingness are the most favorable for giving intrinsic motivation for the activity. As a result, we may assume that working settings that foster positive connections with colleagues and clients (Lopes, 2011) or promote independence or self-development (Turban & Yan, 2016) will result in greater levels of eudaimonic well-being.

The study of Nangoy et al. (2020) revealed that an employee’s job well-being has a strong, positive influence on work performance. A workplace environment that promotes eudaimonic well-being is heavily influenced by the particular employer, the department or team in which the employee works, and even the contents of the job role itself. Working increases eudaimonic well-being. The degree to which one achieves eudaimonic well-being through employment is significantly reliant on the nature of one’s job. To begin, there is a definite vertical association between particular employment and eudaimonic well-being. Perhaps more importantly, there is a horizontal relationship between the work position and eudaimonic well-being (Polidori & Teobaldelli, 2013; Binder, 2016). Employee performance is significantly influenced by eudaimonic well-being (Kousznik, Peiró, & Soriano, 2019). Promoting employee psychological well-being may be beneficial to the organization (Kundi et al., 2020).

The pursuit/experience of eudaimonic pleasure improves job performance (Kousznik, Peiró, & Soriano, 2019). Servant leadership was found to be favorably associated with workplace results, owing in part to eudaimonic well-being (der Kinderen et al., 2020). According to the findings of Benjamin et al. (2014), Adler et al. (2017), and Dolan et al. (2017), individuals appreciate eudaimonic well-being but to a smaller extent than hedonic well-being. Eudaimonic well-being broadens the concept of positive psychological well-being by including existential and motivational aspects of healthy functioning, including having a sense of purpose in life, personal progress, positive relations, and real self-expression (Waterman, 2013). Servant leadership was found to be strongly connected with employee eudaimonic well-being (Armour, 2020).

In a perspective where our workforce’s well-being is critical to maintaining a sensitive financial, political, and social balance, it seems reasonable to activate all possible avenues towards well-being, not only in hedonic terms of happiness and satisfaction but also in eudaimonic terms that go beyond feeling better to acquiring psychological properly functioning (Sonnetag, 2015). Employee experiences influence work-related well-being, which evolves and fluctuates (Sonnetag, 2015). As for how organizations gain competitive advantages has shifted from increased output and efficiency to providing distinct services and expertise, and finally to providing meaningful social networks and experiences (Rigby & Ryan, 2018). In an organizational environment, the fulfillment of the meaning and purpose of the job for the worker is certainly critical to the person’s overall well-being (Rothausen, 2013).

In a period of the global financial crisis (European Commission, 2009), when individuals are increasingly confronting job instability and layoff changes, the promotion of well-being becomes critical for both companies and society at large (Keyes & Grzywacz, 2005). Given these circumstances, the current study sought to propose a eudaimonic state of well-being. This narrative review was based on an examination of 10 journals on employees’ eudaimonic well-being. We also looked at the factors that influence eudaimonic well-being. We

looked specifically at the relationship between eudaimonic well-being at work, also known as optimum human functioning (Deci & Ryan, 2001), and job performance. Taking all of these factors into account might aid in developing remedy suggestions.

Methods

Criteria of Selection

This narrative review featured review papers and original research on the issue of employees' eudaimonic well-being. We did not define a yearly range because the topic is new and we wanted to see what was in the literature overall. Papers that investigated various factors of eudaimonic well-being and their influence on job performance were included. The search results were then restricted to English-language papers, peer-reviewed, and academic journals.

Search Strategy

Different databases: Google Scholar, PubMed, Scopus, PsychInfo, ScienceDirect, and MedLine were used to search for articles in social sciences, management sciences, and medicine or psychology journals, guided by topic-related search terms. Different keywords in English were entered, including eudaimonic well-being, employees' eudaimonic well-being, eudaimonic well-being factors, job performance, etc. The selected literature was then reviewed systemically and combined for this narrative review.

Procedure

The authors conducted independent research for articles using several keywords and descriptors, as well as the abstract and title. The entire texts of these articles were obtained and analyzed for eligibility using the inclusion criteria mentioned above, generating a total of 60 eligible papers that satisfied the set criteria. Using this strategy, we also checked the references of the selected publications and included 30 more studies. The entire texts of articles that met abstract and title reviews and satisfied the inclusion criteria were independently evaluated by members of the research team. A total of 90 articles were investigated. Each article was evaluated based on several criteria, including study design, size of the sample, sample characteristics, setting, and theoretical methods behind the investigations into employees' eudaimonic well-being, eudaimonic well-being factors, and eudaimonic well-being effects. Finally, 10 publications met all of the requirements for including quantitative and qualitative data, as well as review studies on employees' eudaimonic well-being. The study team used a defined procedure to extract and code the data, and the results were briefly described.

Results

Table 1 presents the outcomes of our search method.

Table 1. Studies on the well-being, employees' eudaimonic well-being, factors of eudaimonic well-being, and effects of eudaimonic well-being.

Author, year	Study design	Key findings
Steptoe et al., (2007)	Cross-sectional study	Good sleep is closely related to eudaimonic well-being, which may mitigate the influence of psychological risk factors.
Rothausen, (2013)	Empirical study	The purpose and meaning of the job for the employee are most likely critical to the person's general well-being, as well as their engagement with and motivation toward their job in a given organizational environment.
Sonnentag, (2015)	Empirical study	Employee well-being is impacted by work experiences, which has an impact on job performance and other behaviors of job.
Inceoglu et al., (2018)	Review paper	Employees' eudaimonic well-being has been linked to higher job performance.
Kożusznik, Peiró, & Soriano(2019)	Multilevel diary design	Extra-role performance was found to be positively influenced by eudaimonic well-being.
der Kinderen et al., (2020)	Cross-sectional design	When the workplace civility atmosphere was high, servant leadership had a higher association with eudaimonic well-being.
Armour, (2020)	Cross-sectional study	The findings revealed that both transformational and the relationship between servant and leadership were considerably positively related to employee eudaimonic well-being.
Kundi et al., (2020)	Cross-sectional design	The relationship between eudaimonic well-being and employee job performance is mediated by affective commitment. Furthermore, perceived work uncertainty mitigates the relationship between affective commitment and eudaimonic well-being.
Nangoy et al., (2020)	Cross-sectional design	Work well-being has a favorable influence on job performance. It is proposed that employers increase their employees' performance by emphasizing things that would enhance work well-being.
Koburtay, & Alzoubi(2021)	Cross-sectional design	The findings show that employees who have spiritual experiences at work have better eudaimonic well-being.

In organizations, psychologists have frequently attempted to focus on both employee productivity and well-being to attain long-term well-being and performance. Kożusznik, Peiró, and Soriano (2019) found that eudaimonic well-being had a significant degree of short-term fluctuation in research with a sample (n=83) of white-collar employees. Employees' levels of eudaimonic well-being and extra-role performance have a substantially positive association.

Job-related well-being is the contributor of the employment to well-being via the fulfillment of the job's purposes for the individual. Fulfillment of employment purpose includes six aspects: development and growth, financial sustainability and flourishing, influence on the family as self-defined, impact on life construction, role in society, and self-expression. According to Rothausen's (2013) empirical study, fulfillment of the purpose and meaning of the job for the worker is probably crucial to the person's general well-being as well as their engagement in and motivation toward their work in a given organizational environment.

The emphasis on pleasure, work engagement, or job satisfaction as techniques for boosting the performance of an organization may come at the expense of individuals' psychological well-being and functioning. der Kinderen et al. (2020) used a sample of 312 employees to investigate the influence of relationships between servant and leadership and workplace civility atmosphere on eudaimonic well-being. The findings revealed that when the workplace civility atmosphere was high, servant leadership had a greater association with eudaimonic well-being. Moreover, the findings revealed that servant leadership was positively associated with workplace outcomes, mediated in part by eudaimonic well-being and that this mediating procedure changed across different degrees of workplace civility environment.

In workplaces, psychologists have frequently attempted to increase employees' well-being and performance, which may be accomplished through a variety of means. In a study of 68 office workers, Kożusznik, Peiró, and Soriano, (2019) discovered that "paths from or through eudaimonia" are more effective strategies to boost work performance. Pursuing/experiencing eudaimonic pleasure is more favorable to job performance. It shows that eudaimonic well-being is a significant predictor of performance.

Sleep disorders are linked to poorer cognitive performance, chronic sickness, poor mental health, and early death. Steptoe et al. (2007) discovered that negative psychosocial characteristics such as financial hardship, social isolation, limited emotional support, negative interpersonal relationships, and psychological problems were connected to reported sleep issues in research with a sample (n = 736) of males and females. When eudaimonic well-being was included, the intensity of these relationships decreased by 20–73%, indicating that positive psychological states were partially mediating the effects. These findings suggest that eudaimonic well-being is directly related to excellent sleep and may mitigate the influence of psychological risk factors.

The eudaimonic viewpoint defines well-being as more than just happiness. This viewpoint emphasizes psychological well-being and sees happiness as an important component of well-being, but not as the sole indication, necessitating the addition of additional self-fulfillment markers. Nangoyet al. (2020) discovered that employee work well-being had a significant, beneficial influence on job performance in research using a sample (n = 509) of millennial employees.

The success and productivity of an organization are inextricably linked with its employees' performance. Kundi et al., (2020) found that emotional commitment modulates the relationship between psychological well-being (eudaimonic) and employee work performance in a sample (n = 280) of Pakistanis companies employees. Furthermore, perceived work instability dampens the relationship between psychological well-being (eudaimonic) and emotional commitment. Promoting employee psychological well-being may be beneficial to the organization. However, if efforts to ensure job security are not implemented, it may lead to negative employee work-related behavior and attitudes.

Leadership has a significant influence on employee mental health. According to the findings of Armour's (2020) research, both transformational and the relationship between servant and leadership were substantially positively related to employee eudaimonic well-being. Transformational leadership is a better predictor of eudaimonic well-being among employees. Furthermore, it was shown that a leader's eudaimonic well-being was not substantially related to an employee's eudaimonic well-being.

Through motivational mediators, transformational leadership was found to be positively connected to eudaimonic well-being. Employee behavior, performance, ingenious work involvement, and well-being are all influenced by leadership behavior (Janjua & Malik, 2017). The findings of the Inceoglu et al., (2018) study demonstrated that employee eudaimonic well-being is associated with improved performance, but a shift in our thinking will allow us to be more aware of well-being performance.

The eudaimonic experience of satisfaction and purpose that a person has is referred to as well-being. Employee well-being is impacted by work experiences, which have an impact on task performance and other behaviors on the job. Sonnentag (2015) found that job-related well-being alters and fluctuates depending on the experiences employees have at work. Changes in well-being, in turn, predict changes in performance, as well as perceived workplace features and work-home variables.

Discussion

Individuals are spending a lot of time at work, and it is becoming a major source of purpose and identification in their lives. For a long time, scholars have studied the feeling of psychological meaningfulness at work as an essential component that impacts the behavior of employees (Kożusznik, Peiró, & Soriano, 2019). Eudaimonic well-being is significant, maybe especially in light of an ever-increasing range of job settings and worker diversity. The current study sought to investigate the factors influencing workers' eudaimonic well-being. The goal of this study was to examine the association between eudaimonic well-being and work performance. Previous studies have mostly explored the nature and factors influencing eudaimonic well-being. As the study of Sonnentag's (2015) research focused on the dynamics of well-being through people's hedonic and eudaimonic experiences. Similarly, Nangoyet al. (2020) found that well-being is constructed on two fundamental philosophical foundations: the hedonic viewpoint, or happiness, and the eudaimonic viewpoint, or self-actualization.

One critical aspect was to establish how EWB was conceived and formalized in empirical studies aiming to link it to performance. We discovered several features that lead to numerous noteworthy patterns. To start with, Rothausen, (2013) concentrated on engagement, which makes sense given that it is a concept intimately tied to performance, particularly the sorts of performance that extend beyond in-role activities. It was found that eudaimonic well-being at work is heavily influenced by the type of one's job. A job role and eudaimonic well-being have a clear vertical link. Previous studies have found a relationship between job performance and eudaimonic well-being as an emotional term. The study by Inceoglu et al. (2018) extends this to eudaimonic well-being in terms of full function. This research provides a deeper understanding of what it means to experience eudaimonic well-being at work.

Conclusions

Through reviewing the previous studies, this paper established comprehensively an association between employees' eudaimonic well-being and their performance. According to the findings of this study, the type of one's work is a major factor in determining one's level of eudaimonic well-being. A positive relationship between leadership and employees increases eudaimonic well-being and, as a result, organizational productivity. A workplace environment that promotes eudaimonic well-being is heavily influenced by the particular employer, the department or team in which the employee works, and even the contents of the job role itself. Employee job performance is mediated by eudaimonic well-being, which is connected to commitment. This study effectively demonstrated the considerable, beneficial influence of employment eudaimonic well-being on job performance.

Limitation and Recommendation

Due to the limited time, this study was limited to articles that investigated eudaimonic well-being and job performance. Future studies can be conducted on the vast number of articles and relationships between eudaimonic well-being and an individual's mental health. The organization will be able to increase its employees' performance through positive methods that emphasize characteristics that will promote work well-being. Workplace well-being enhancement projects require organizational design, involve significant resources, have an impact on the organization as a whole, and are long-term in nature. As a result, the execution of such initiatives necessitates the participation of higher leaders in policy decisions. Interventions to improve employees' job well-being can be delivered at three levels. The primary level is concerned with designing a work environment that has an impact on individual well-being and includes elements such as job redesign, flexible working, work culture reform, and work-life balance regulations. The secondary level is intended to increase individuals' resilience, competencies, and knowledge in dealing with work pressures, such as through improved leadership and management methods. At this level, interventions may take the shape of improved recruiting and selection procedures, the establishment of management programs aimed at improving employee eudaimonic well-being, training in stress management, and forms of physical activity. Finally, the tertiary level is geared towards assisting workers who are experiencing challenges, either at work or in other parts of their lives, through counseling or employee support programs. Eudaimonic well-being at work has been demonstrated to improve job performance. The study's findings may be used at both the micro and macroeconomic levels in terms of how to establish self-sustaining relationships between individual eudaimonic well-being and individual productivity.

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